

Robotic Gantry System for Point Cloud Modeling

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Abstract—We present a robotic gantry system that we use to acquire point cloud data on close-range (15-60 *cm*) objects. We developed an Arduino-based control system and synchronized it with new depth sensor drivers in preparation for autonomously acquiring three-dimensional models of biological plant growth. Our models contain tens of thousands of XYZ coordinates with color values. Our system filters and inputs a stream of thousands of images taken from various perspectives in a two-dimensional plane, and is capable of registering those images into a single three-dimensional coordinate system. We have currently implemented an iterative closest point and normal curvature algorithm from the Point Cloud Library. These calculations do not perform optimally and we need to overcome the problem of silhouette aliasing, where edge points have terribly inaccurate depth values, if we are to develop the best possible models given our camera and system constraints.

I. INTRODUCTION

Through cheap new cameras for precise spatial and color mapping of physical objects, many new industrial applications become viable. Autonomous spatial modeling and analysis for industrial agriculture is one important application that promises profound global socioeconomic rewards, particularly through scalable swarm robotic experiments for testing and optimizing genetic and nutritional engineering. To demonstrate principles of this application, we built a robotic imaging system with a cheap new short range depth sensor, and developed algorithms for processing those images in preparation for biological analytics. Our imaging system uses a gantry crane that can move a camera mounted on a carriage to any position in a plane of 1.83 by 2.46 meters. The value of the gantry is that it can be automatically operated for novel point cloud modeling experiments of biology dynamics in its field of view, over a span of months - entire lifecycles of plant growth.

Virtually every mass-manufactured (*i.e.* inexpensive) depth sensor commercially available over the past five years, such as the Microsoft Kinect [1] or ASUS Xtion PRO [2], could only map objects beyond 60 *cm* from the camera: they were not designed for short range precision analytics. But with Intel's new short range depth sensor [3], and the promise of more short range depth sensors to come for consumer applications in gesture recognition and augmented reality, new industrial opportunities for distributed spatial intelligence are created. These sensors typically are one-tenth the cost of the cheapest two-dimensional laser scanners [4]. We take advantage of these economics by calibrating and developing drivers for an Intel depth sensor to image and process XYZ coordinates and colors on objects; and we integrate these drivers with a robotic gantry for autonomously collecting massive datasets. We present results in registering these images into one digital 3D model of

our imaging environment with Point Cloud Library algorithms [5]. Finally, we discuss the current limitations of our approach and the hurdles we must overcome to improve our models for analytical applications like volumetric recording and object recognition.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Gantry Control System

Our gantry system moves a camera to any position in a 1.83 x 2.46 *m* frame, for imaging objects placed on one of three shelves, each 0.61 x 0.61 x 2.46 *m*. We placed a series of strawberry plants for observation on each of these shelves. Two slides are mounted to the front of the frame to allow horizontal and vertical movement of the metal carriage that holds the camera. This carriage is mounted to the back of the vertical slide and a control panel is mounted at the top of the vertical slide. The position of the camera carriage is dictated by two belt drives and the belt drives are controlled by a pair of stepper motors. One belt drive moves the camera carriage along the vertical slide and the other moves the vertical slide along the horizontal one. The step size is 0.0113 *mm* for the horizontal motor and 0.0253 *mm* for the vertical motor. The stepper motors and their respective EasyDriver drivers are located on the control panel. The control panel houses an Arduino micro-controller [6] that interfaces with the stepper motor drivers for algorithmic control. Each motor has two pins assigned to the Arduino: one for direction and the other for toggling a step in that direction. Four additional pins on the Arduino are used as edge-detector switches, positioned to prevent the camera carriage from going beyond the four edges of the gantry frame.

B. Point Cloud Camera

For 3D mapping through the gantry system, we developed drivers for the CREATIVE Interactive Gesture Camera [3] using the Intel Perceptual Computing SDK [8] as our API. This camera emits and receives an infrared signal to measure depth, with a maximum resolution of 320 x 240 pixels for objects located about 15-100 *cm* from it. The camera is capable of producing 30 frames per second, while our integrated robotic imaging system captures data more slowly because it relies on acknowledgements sent across a local area network between an Arduino-controlled gantry and Windows-controlled camera imaging drivers.

C. Synchronization of Gantry and Point Cloud Camera

As Fig. 2 shows, two computers automate the interface between our Arduino micro-controller, point cloud camera,

Fig. 1. Robotic gantry system for capturing point cloud images of plants along a two-dimensional plane (horizontal and vertical motion). Identified are the power source, Arduino micro-controller, Ethernet port, horizontal and vertical stepper motors and shafts, vertical stepper belt, one of the edge stoppers (top), and the carriage on which the point cloud camera is bolted.

Fig. 2. Diagram of the communication between the Arduino micro-controller, point cloud camera, Windows and Linux machines for control of our robotic gantry system. UDP packets are sent from the Arduino to the Windows machine to synchronize the images and transfer odometry data, and UDP packets are sent back from the Windows machine to the Arduino after images finish to continue the loop. Through USB connection the Windows machine takes an image whenever it receives a UDP packet from the Arduino. All images are automatically forwarded to a Linux machine via WinSCP for ROS and Point Cloud Library processing.

Fig. 3. Arduino micro-controller with Ethernet shield. All pins that are unused are forwarded to headers at top.

and Point Cloud Library algorithms. A Windows machine runs drivers of the Intel camera, which is optimized for parallelization on Intel Core processors. It controls the camera via USB cable. It also controls the Arduino via an Ethernet shield input with an Ethernet cable. Once point cloud images are captured, they are automatically transferred to a Linux machine for processing via the ROS-based Point Cloud Library.

After positioning the camera by algorithmic instructions from the Windows machine, the gantry provides an estimate in millimeters of the position of the camera in its two dimensional plane of freedom. We developed upon an open source stepper motor library called AccelStepper [7] to control the stepper motors and acquire calibration data from the gantry system. This library offers an API for easy access to position data and meticulous control of motor movement.

When the system starts up for the first time it positions the camera at a reference origin to establish a virtual coordinate system. It does this by moving at low speed until the carriage that carries the camera is located at the top left corner of the frame. The motors move one at a time and only stop when the edge indicator switches on their axes are triggered. After the camera carriage is in position, the system starts to incrementally move the carriage and take images. The distance between consecutive images is configurable down to the value of a single step on each axis; however, the time it takes to obtain coverage of all plants under observation is a constraint that favors larger distances between images. The process of taking an image can be broken down into several intermediate steps. First of all, the Arduino tells the motors to move a set number of steps to reach the position where the next image will be taken. The AccelStepper library ensures that the carriage will accelerate as it starts and stops to minimize belt drive slippage and retain positional accuracy. Once the carriage is in place, the current position relative to the origin is recorded. This odometry information is extracted from the motors as a number of steps and is then converted to millimeters. These position values are sent to the Windows machine through Ethernet by User Datagram Protocol (UDP). The Arduino development environment makes it easy to trans-

for UDP packets with an Ethernet library. This library handles communication with the Arduino Ethernet shield and simplifies establishing the Arduino as a node on the network. Once the Arduino's MAC address and port number are specified and the destination IP address and port number are specified then the buffer containing our odometry data can be handed off and sent over the network.

On the Windows machine a Python script acts as a listener for the UDP packets sent from the Arduino. The script reads the odometry data sent in the UDP packet and passes it as an argument into a driver for recording point clouds from the Intel camera that we wrote. The driver saves the image data with the odometry data as its filename, so individual images can easily be identified by the location they were taken, a measurement that may become useful in calculating point cloud transformation for iterative closest point and other registration algorithms. Once the image driver exits, the Python listener program sends the Arduino a reply UDP packet to signal that it can move to the next position. To avoid deadlock in the gantry's operation, the image driver is spawned as a subprocess. If the driver takes longer than 6 seconds to run, it is automatically terminated and the UDP packet is sent back to the Arduino to signal it to continue.

The Arduino code goes to sleep after sending the odometry data to the Windows machine, and does not wake up until the Windows machine replies with a go-ahead message. This ensures that the gantry avoids moving while an image is being taken, and it ensures that the Arduino and Windows machine stay synchronized. After the Arduino receives a response packet from the Windows machine, it begins continues in its loop to move the camera to its next location.

Once the gantry finishes all image capturing for its current session - the longest sessions of which we ran for 36 hours - a Python script uses WinSCP on the Windows machine automatically transfers all of the point cloud images to our Linux machine. The reason for needing to transfer all of the images across machines is that the Intel camera is only operational on Windows at the time of writing, when the camera is still in a beta testing mode, while point cloud processing algorithms from the Point Cloud Library (PCL) and Robotic Operating System (ROS) are predominantly designed for Linux operating systems.

D. Point Cloud Image Capture and Pre-Filtering

Our algorithm for capturing images scans through every pixel in the 320 x 240 depth grid. We save depth values that are real numbers within desirable distance boundaries and filter out all others (*i.e.* values that could not be a plant are filtered). We use a UV transform to convert depth values into the same coordinate system as color values, and save all color values for which a real depth value exists as type RGB32. If the color value is saturated (*i.e.* completely white) then we discard that point too. Once a point has been established as having desirable depth and color values, we iterate out point counter and finish looping through all pixels. Finally, we save all points recorded into a .pcd file format [9], or point cloud data format, as defined by the Point Cloud Library (PCL). Saving our data in this format enables quick use of PCL algorithms, which are currently the essence of our image processing analyses. We

Fig. 4. Filtered calibrated colored point cloud in comparison with a standard color image from a similar perspective. The colored cloud has been slightly rotated, so its precision is not optimal.

physically calibrated our point cloud camera by making its face perpendicular to its base, using a straight-edge as shown in Fig. 4; and we placed plants as close as possible to the point cloud camera, according to its technical specifications: we physically postured plants so that as much of their mass as possible is as close to 15 cm away from the camera as possible.

E. Registration of Point Cloud Sequences

Extensive discoveries were made by processing algorithms for registering our point clouds. First, dozens of hours were invested in exploring a state-of-the-art iterative closest point mapper from the Autonomous Systems Lab at ETH Zurich [10], [11]. It is comprehensive by design – “*a convenient way to tune, test, and deploy several registration solutions using the same node*” [12]. Convenience is a matter of perspective, however, and their package is not designed for reading discrete images formatted in the .pcd style of the Point Cloud Library (PCL), even though PCL is thoroughly integrated with ROS, and the ETH-Z ICP package is built for ROS and uses PCL data structures.

Nonetheless, we are able to successfully publish our Intel point cloud data to RViz, and have it read in a `sensor_msgs::PointCloud2` data structure through a ROS publisher targeting the ROS topic `depth_registered/points` and transformation frame `openni_rgb_optical_frame` that ETH-Z algorithms demand. In fact, we are able to run their ICP package perfectly with an ASUS Xtion Pro; and we can plug our .pcd ROS clouds into the ETH-Z package without problem. The roadblock we face is a seemingly endless stack of parameter debugging, in a fashion that is not necessary for devices with already-developed OpenNI drivers for Linux. The Intel device does have OpenNI drivers for providing myriad calibration information, but it is not currently compatible with Linux and is heavily optimized for the Windows OS; optimization is not our concern, but we would prefer not to develop new operating system drivers for such a complex device if that is not necessary. We therefore suspended our efforts with the ETH-Z registration algorithm at least temporarily, even though we remain tantalized by its carefully organized framework for layering filtering, nearest neighbor matching, feature extraction, and error stabilizations – for point clouds with XYZ and RGB data. It turns out that integrating color

Fig. 5. (i) One filtered, calibrated point cloud for baseline comparison; (ii) depth-encoding of the same exact cloud in the prior panel, where colors represent depth (Z) value; (iii) same cloud as prior panels but with a 30° rotation – shown here to highlight silhouette aliasing effects where cloud edges have unreliable data; (iv) registering of 3 images taken within 2 centimeters of each other using the Rusu curvature-based algorithm [13] – we see obvious patterns duplicated that indicate the algorithm converged poorly; (v) rotation of the registered cloud in the prior panel by 30° to show more duplicated features, such as the aliased blue tails and identical top-right red leaves in the left plant; (vi) aerial view of the registered cloud to show good news about the depth data – the yellow plant pot on the top right has a nearly perfect circle curvature, meaning that depth values for at least that component were measured with very high precision.

data into registration is not standard for all other algorithms that we were able to register our data with.

We easily implemented PCL registration code by Radu Bogdan Rusu [13] for registering two pairs of point clouds. The algorithm is based on a simple iterative search for a transformation between two coordinate systems assumed to be in the same global frame. It optionally down-samples the data. While accumulating potential transformations across several iterations per pair registration, if the difference between the transform for iteration N and N-1 is smaller than a given threshold, then a smaller maximum correspondence is chosen between the source and target. This drives one of the transformation possibilities out of business, and enables a winning transformation to be chosen. The winning transform is inverted to be oriented from target to source, and it is applied to the target cloud. The transformed target is then integrated with the source, and the process is all repeated starting with the new combined cloud, if there any additional clouds to register.

III. RESULTS

Fig. 5 highlights our most important results to date. We see that our single filtered, calibrated color point cloud has reasonably high quality, and we are able to examine the depth coordinates through color encoding to visualize three spatial dimensions in a two-dimensional plane. Importantly, we have identified clearly a problem that must be addressed: silhouette aliasing. This is a common problem with point cloud images, and solutions involve edge detection and recombination [14],

[15]. Fortunately, the Intel point cloud camera, developed by SoftKinetic, has a built-in API for accessing "confidence" scalars for weighting the quality of each point [16]. This will certainly help in filtering out depth coordinates probabilistically determined to be false.

However, as Fig. 6 demonstrates, certain objects with tight small edges seem to be very poorly mapped overall by the point cloud camera, even at an optimal distance. The pair of scissors stacked on a roll of tape is an example of these limitations. In particular, by filtering out values with low-confidence – handles of the scissors – a resulting cloud would be missing a key part of this real world object. This is why a confidence map alone will not solve this problem. Rosenthal and Linsen demonstrate anti-aliasing methods in [14], [15], some of which rely on recombining points based on density clustering. Such a proactive cloud grooming approach may prove essential to using the Intel camera for analytics of real plant growth.

Finally, Fig. 7 shows three different angles on a poorly-converging registration algorithm run amok: 20 point clouds are combined into a single image that technically should span 4 unique plants, but more closely resembles an alien creature from Europa.

IV. DISCUSSION

It remains to be seen to what extent solving the silhouette aliasing problem in our point cloud data will make cloud registration of plants precise. Objects with large rounded

Fig. 6. (i) Well-defined shapes for testing point cloud aliasing; (ii) depth-encoding of the same exact cloud in the prior panel, where colors represent depth (Z) value; (iii) same cloud as prior panels but with a 30° rotation – shown here to highlight silhouette aliasing effects where cloud edges have unreliable data.

Fig. 7. (i) 20 point clouds of complex plant shapes registered together ineffectively – notice duplicated patterns; (ii) same cloud as prior panels but with a 45° rotation to highlight silhouette aliasing effects in blue; (iii) front of same cloud facing downward, with the red object representing some false coagulation point for the algorithm.

curves and convex surfaces – *e.g.* faces – seem to be mapped far more precisely than complex objects with many small curves, like strawberry plants. As demonstrated in Fig. 6 with the mystery of the missing scissor handles, very large amounts of depth data may be skewed so much that the original image is unrecognizable. This was the case with application of registration algorithms to our data. Further, the fact that our registration algorithms did not account for color data is an obvious issue. The blue color of the scissor handles, *e.g.*, could easily be correlated as unique within a specific localized image-space. We therefore aim to add color to the Rusu registration algorithm or finish debugging and writing drivers for ETH-Z ICP parameter initialization from .pcd files. We also wonder whether the gantry imaging system would be more useful if it was designed to traverse 360° around the target object. It is extremely difficult for us to even try developing complete 3D models on objects when only one side of the object can be observed automatically by our existing system.

V. CONCLUSION

We developed a robotic gantry system for large-scale point cloud imaging of objects, particularly plants. We have established the data collection foundations for extended experiments that study biological growth, while we have also

identified several aspects of our existing algorithmic and cloud processing solution that should be addressed before proceeding with experiments. We hope to solve the problem of silhouette aliasing through a combination of confidence metrics and density clustering (preferably in a way that leverages color).

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